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Eucharist as *The Medicine of Life* in St Ephrem

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EUCHARIST AS *MEDICINE OF LIFE* IN ST EPHREM

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

Due to political and cultural reasons, the western theological schools have forgotten the Christian Theology from the Semitic Culture¹ for a long time. Even though there was a time when many of the ecclesiastical authorities of the West considered the prayers and the theological works written in Semitic, especially in Syriac language, as heresy, by the beginning of the 19th century, the said misconception was slowly removed from the mind of the Western Theologians. At present, the Oriental Theologians search for the Syriac Theological Sources to unleash its richness to the entire Catholic Church.

The proposed dissertation entitled “Eucharist as *the Medicine of Life* in St Ephrem” attempts to study the pattern of Ephrem’s way of theologization with particular reference to the Eucharistic imagery of *the Medicine of Life*. This thesis primarily examines the historical, cultural, and linguistic sources from which St. Ephrem the Syrian has adopted the said Eucharistic imagery for theologization and analyzes how this imagery is used to explain the different aspects of the Holy Eucharist. The primary purpose of this study is to analyze the shift of meaning in the Eucharistic imagery of *the Medicine of Life*. Why is it significant? This analysis will teach a person how to understand an imagery or any form of expression in religious language and theological language. Therefore, this thesis not only studies the ‘what’ aspect of the theologization but also the ‘how’ and ‘why’ aspects. To better clarify these aspects of the postmodern world, I have coined and incorporated specific new terms to explain the pattern of the theologization to the present generation. Therefore, I have used ‘transcendental leap’, ‘neuro context (NC)’, ‘fragmentary neuro context’

¹ “‘Persian Christianity’ refers to East Syriac Christianity under the Sasanian Empire and beyond.” Cf. C. Buck, *Paradise and Paradigm: Key Symbols in Persian Christianity and the Bahai Faith* (New York: State University of New York Press, 1999) 3.

and ‘collective neuro context’ to analyze the Eucharistic imagery better in *the Medicine of Life*.

All these terms represent the formation of an idea and its shift of meaning. The semantic change is indicated with the term transcendental leap (TL). Transcending the leap cannot be understood as a synonym with the semantic shift in linguistics (suggestiveness). At the same time, it goes beyond the physical world to the metaphysical world. Therefore, TL is the process of interpreting divine revelation in the human language. For example, the meaning of ‘New Jerusalem’ is not ‘a modern Jerusalem’ when TL takes place. The said phrase will get an eschatological interpretation. What will be the situation if this eschatological dimension of the meaning is not transferred to the reader? When we deal with the religious language and theological language, TL is a necessary linguistic phenomenon. Therefore, in TL, both the process of meaning generation and the semantic leap are included. In typical cases, semantic change is the result of cognition. Whereas in TL, it is the result of cognition, contemplation, and divine revelation. Where does and how does this complex process take place?

The direct answer for this question is the brain with the neural network, which is exposed to sensory experiences and divine revelation. In this thesis, I do not intend to enter directly into any physiological explanations. Still, I will be using the terms such as *Neuro Context* (NC), *Fragmentary Neuro Context* (FNC), and *Collective Neuro Context* (CNC) since these terms are my inventions to explain the Theo-semantic phenomenon *Transcendental Leap* (TL). I am giving a short introduction to the use of these terms (see Figure 1). The term *Neuro Context* stands for the complete sensory information and the capacity to cobble new ideas using existing information. It means that *Neuro Context* is always dynamic and open-ended. Therefore, *Neuro Context* can be defined as the total of the received data, the neural ability to manipulate data to generate new knowledge,

the ability to go beyond the data at the same time to contact the contemporary context.²

Neuro Context is always connected to *Collective Neuro Context (CNS)*, as it is portrayed in *Figure 1*. Since it is dynamic in its very nature, it is constantly widening until it ceases to exist. When a person hears, sees, touches, tastes, or smells something, the data become part of the *Neuro Context*. The reason for combining the words ‘neuro’ and ‘context’ is to indicate the neural activity and the space where it takes place. Therefore, the words ‘neuro’ and ‘context’ in the term *Neuro Context* stands for continuous neural networking and the brain. Since I am not dealing directly with neurolinguistics here in this thesis, I’ll focus on the ideological aspect of *Neuro Context*. Why *Neuro Context* becomes significant is that it will help a person how to read religious and theological works. *Neuro Contextual Analysis*

² Cf. J.John, “Neuro Contextual Analysis of Sacramental Symbols” *Ensygloge: An International Journal for Arts and Science* (January-June, 2021, Published on 1st June 2021, Vol 1, Issue 1),p.2 [<https://www.ensygloge.com>](accessed October, 2021)

enables a person to understand how a theologian thought. This analysis helps analyze the process of theologization.

Now I will explain how the *Neuro Contextual Analysis* functions. As you see in *Figure 1*, there are many factors included in CNC, such as Divine Revelation, Nature, Culture, People, Available Knowledge, and so on. *Neuro Context* is the product of the CNC to which NC is part. As a result of continuous dialogue with CNC, a person's *Neuro Context* starts developing. Slowly *Neuro Context* produces *Fragmentary Neuro Context* (FNC). Any expression, literary work, artwork, etc., are coming under *Fragmentary Neuro Context*. That means within a life time a person creates millions of *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts*. The preserved *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts* are used for references (Like a book of an author). It means that each *Fragmentary Neuro Context* points to the source from which it originated (i.e., NC). No one gets a direct entry to anyone's *Neuro Context* without the help of an available *Fragmentary Neuro Context*. Therefore, the proper understanding of any *Fragmentary Neuro Context* primarily demands research in the CNC and other *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts* of the NC of the author.

If the author is NC^1 , then the reader is NC^2 as is portrayed in *Figure 1*. When the reader starts exploring NC^1 , at least four types of dialogue are indicated in the picture with arrows.

- a. $NC^2 - FNC^1 - NC^2 - FNC^2$ (TL^1 and TL^2 will be similar or advanced)
- b. $NC^2 - CNC^1 - FNC^1 - FNC^2$ (TL^1 and TL^2 will be similar or advanced)
- c. $NC^2 - FNC^1 - CNC^1 - FNC^2$ (TL^1 and TL^2 will be similar or advanced)
- d. $NC^2 - FNC^1 - FNC^2$ (TL^1 and TL^2 will be not identical but advanced)

In the case of religious language and theological language, a unique linguistic phenomenon is called *Transcendental Leap* (TL). It means that each religious or theological work generates a shift in meaning in the reader's mind. That means when this shift happens, the signifier transcends its limits, bringing the reader's minds to the signified, which is metaphysical or divine. It is the result of the *Transcendental Leap* in the NC^2 (reader). If the reader is not accustomed to the CNC^1 and FNC^1 , the desired leap will not take place, but there will be a

kind of Transcendental Leap as in the case of 'd'. The *Transcendental Leap* is always directed to God and the economy of salvation. *Neuro contextual analysis* studies how this transcendental leap occurs.

So if a person is 20 years old, that person's *Neuro Context* consists of 20 years' entire experiences and the continuous generation of ideas by using the past and present experiences. It means that a person's *Neuro Context* is always influenced by the society and the culture to which he-she e is part. That means the person's *Neuro Context* is always in communication with the existing *Neuro Contexts* (CNC). This connected network of existing *Neuro Contexts* is known as *Collective Neuro Context* (CNC). It means a person is born into the matrix of CNC. Therefore, it is necessary to know the particular CNC to which a new *Neuro Context* is exposed to trace out the exact meaning of all the meaning of the *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts* (FNC). *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts* refer to all the stored or preserved data or information outside a person in any form available to others. It is part of the CNC because NC is constantly in dialogue with CNC. For example, if I write a book, make a phrase or a statement, draw a picture or make a gesture, it becomes a *Fragmentary Neuro Context*. It means that *Fragmentary Neuro Context* itself emanates either from *Neuro Context* or from the *Collective Neuro Context*. It is visible. It is the connecting link to NC and CNC. It has the capability of causing *Transcendental Leap*. For example, the Eucharistic imagery of *the Medicine of Life* is a *Fragmentary Neuro Context*. To find out the *Transcendental Leap* of this FNC, it is necessary to study how the NC of the author of the said imagery is developed and to which CNC the author and the reader were exposed. It also means that there are many CNCs influences a particular NC. Therefore, every FNC is the outcome of the facilitated version from the NC. This is an open-ended process. It means that this process never stops. It means that such a small phrase will generate different levels of meaning and culminate it in the Transcendental Leap. I will discuss this in the succeeding chapters.

Since this study takes place in the 21st century, it is impossible to get a direct entry to the CNC and NC of St Ephrem. Still, it is possible to reason the treasures out of the available resources such as the works of St Ephrem, Secondary Sources about him and his works, and so on. All these are the available Fragmentary Neuro Contexts that direct to the *Neuro Context* and *Collective Neuro Context* of St Ephrem. Otherwise, we will directly associate and interpret the FNC of St Ephrem within our own NCs, which are not exposed to the CNC and NC of St Ephrem, and finally and with an entirely different interpretation of what St Ephrem had not thought of. Therefore, in this thesis, I am trying to analyze how the Eucharistic imagery *the Medicine of Life* has got the *Transcendental Leap* and try to find out the theological meaning encapsulated with the said imagery with the help of *Neuro Contextual Analysis*.

Here I am following the second pattern of dialogue (NC² — CNC¹ — FNC¹ — FNC² [TL¹ and TL² will be similar or advanced]).

Therefore, as depicted in Figure 1, in the first chapter, I will explain the cultural background of St Ephrem (CNC¹). In this chapter, we give a broader look to the formation of the theological formation of St Ephrem. This chapter is significant in understanding the *Transcendental Leap* of the Eucharistic Imagery, *the Medicine of Life*. According to Sebastian Brock, nearly 500 hymns of St Ephrem are available and all these hymns are products of a life of profound and meditative reading of the Scriptures.³ The first chapter of this thesis will study the historical background of St Ephrem along with his influence in Syriac Literature elaborately to build a strong foundation for this academic paper. According to HE Mar Joseph Kallarangattu, the oriental liturgical theology is based on the dictum *Lex Orandi Lex Credendi*.⁴ It means the law of the prayer is the law of Faith. That means the theology in the Church is interpreted within

³ Cf. S. Brock, "A Hymn of St Ephrem on the Eucharist" in *The Harp*, (1987,1988) Vol 1, Issue 1-3, 63.

⁴ Cf. J. Kallarangatt, *Kizhakkinte Daivasastra Aadhyathmika Parambaryangal* (Kottayam: OIRSI, 1999), 18.

the liturgy of the Church. Apart from this background study, the biblical, patristic and liturgical realms also will be given due importance. The main formative influences identified and discussed here are the ancient Mesopotamian, Jewish, and Greek.⁵ This chapter also grants a more comprehensive outlook toward the formation of the theological mind of St Ephrem. The analytical study of the *Transcendental Leap* of the Eucharistic Imagery, *the Medicine of Life*, is further developed in the succeeding chapter with particular reference to its unique use by the fathers of the Church and liturgy of the Malankara Catholic Church.

The main concern of the second chapter is to analyze the use of the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* in the culture in which St Ephrem lived. This chapter also analyses how the concept of the said imagery got into the mind of St Ephrem. Here I explain how the said imagery is preserved and used in the Church along with the different dimensions of the said imagery in the liturgy of the Syro Malankara Catholic Church. This chapter also discusses the various dimensions of the Eucharistic imagery. That means the said imagery stands for the Holy Eucharist and explains the Eucharist's theology from different perspectives. How does it happen full stop because of the power of the word of God? The repeated meditative reading was the cause of the transcendental leap of the said imagery. Therefore, this chapter gives special attention to reading each significant event and concert in the Holy Scripture to find out the Eucharistic theology broad by center frame using the imagery *the Medicine of Life*. This chapter also discusses how the Eucharistic imagery of the Medicine of Life preserved in the virgin because the law of prayer is a law of Faith for the Oriental churches; therefore, this analysis is very significant in building the Eucharistic Theology of the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* in the succeeding chapter.

⁵ Cf. S. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature* (Kottayam: SEERI, 1997) 9.

The imagery of the *Medicine of Life* is one of the critical imageries in the work of St Ephrem. This imagery is the key by which St Ephrem unlocked the mystery of salvation through the Eucharistic theology. Therefore, a detailed search in the work of St Ephrem is required to find out how and what sense the imagery the *Medicine of Life* is used. The third chapter mainly focuses on how St Ephrem has used the term or imagery *the Medicine of Life* to denote the different dimensions of Eucharist. It means this chapter deals with FNC¹. According to Aron C.T. Smith, “Cultural explanations for religion focus on practices and behaviours while cognitive and evolutionary explanations rely on the assumption that Faith comes naturally. At the same time, the neuroscientific evidence suggests that religious thought engages the same brain structures as any strong beliefs, distributed through both emotional rational centers.”⁶ It means that religious cognition and theologization cannot be considered unique forms of cognition, for both are rooted in ordinary representations.⁷ However, this argument cannot be valid ultimately. Though all religious experiences are entrenched in the same structure where all other strong beliefs are centered, stimulation makes the ordinary extraordinary.

In the said case, a kind of transcendental leap of meaning takes place. Modern cognitive science considers it as a kind of paradigmatic grafting where cognitive science builds new explanations by cobbling together old ones from multiple disciplines.⁸ But in the case of transcendental analysis, mere cobbling of ideas may not lead to the Transcend the leap. Here one requires Faith in God. The revealed mystery of salvation is received gradually by submitting oneself humbly before God. When one humbles oneself before God, the divine mysteries will be revealed to him. The revealed mysteries will be understood

⁶ S. Aaron C.T., *Thinking about Religion: Extending the Cognitive Science of Religion*. (Australia: Palgrave Macmillan, 2014), 4.

⁷ Cf. Aaron C.T., *Thinking about Religion: Extending the Cognitive Science of Religion*, 33.

⁸ Cf. Aaron C.T., *Thinking about Religion: Extending the Cognitive Science of Religion*, 76.

and expressed with the available information in the neuro context. It means the transcendental league is the process of understanding the divine mysteries with the eye of Faith by making the fragmentary neuro context within the neuro context. Therefore, in the General Conclusion, I will analyze the transcendental leap of the said Eucharistic imageries to explain how this leap happens in St Ephrem's literature.

Relevance: This study on St Ephrem's use of the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* for symbolizing the Holy Eucharist is relevant because it will give an opening to understanding the Syriac Theology in the present understanding. At one fell swoop, this academic research will provide a better experience of the said Eucharistic imagery by expanding the horizon of the mystery of the Eucharist, the source and summit of the Christian Life through the teachings of St. Ephrem. Apart from this, this thesis will enable one to contextualize the theology.

Methodology: In this work, I use hermeneutic and analytic methods to complete this dissertation.

CHAPTER ONE

AN INTRODUCTION TO ST EPHREM

1.1. Introduction

Every human being is fashioned within the culture of which they are part. Therefore, the study of the works of St Ephrem must begin with a historical search to the Life of St Ephrem to unleash the theological treasures of his works. Ephrem the Syrian (306-373), born in Nisibis and served as a deacon in Edessa, is a prominent Christian theologian poet.⁹ All Churches with apostolic traditions venerate him as a saint. He has written multifarious hymns, poems, sermons, and prose exegesis. According to Paul S. Russel, “Ephrem displays delicacy of touch in his use of scripture.”¹⁰ He used many composite images in his works.¹¹ Sebastian Brock brings a beautiful comparison of the imageries used by St Ephrem, such as ‘the robe of glory’ and ‘*the Medicine of Life*,’ which indicates the sacraments ‘baptism’ and ‘Holy Eucharist’ respectively. He says that a person is gifted the robe of glory and granted the Medicine of Life in the Holy Eucharist in the Baptism.¹² He quotes St Ephrem, “Our Lord baptized human kind with the Holy Spirit, he nourished it with *the Medicine of Life* (Nisibian Hymns 46:8).”¹³ His works were the need of the time because he lived in a society where Arians, Marcionites, Manicheans, Bardaisanites, and such gnostic sects propagated the heresies. Therefore, it is true to say that Ephrem’s majority of the works were intended for defending the true Faith and teachings of the

⁹ Cf. Dr.T. Paniker, “St Ephrem and the Eucharist” in *Aikya Samiksha* (2005) Vol 2, No.1, 5.

Cf. R. Paul S., *St Ephrem the Syrian and St Gregory the Theologian Confront the Aryans* (Kottayam: SEERI, 1994) 11.

¹⁰ Paul S., *St Ephrem the Syrian and St Gregory the Theologian Confront the Aryans*, 41.

¹¹ Cf. Paul S., *St Ephrem the Syrian and St Gregory the Theologian Confront the Aryans*, 86.

¹² Cf. S. Brock, “A Hymn of St Ephrem on the Eucharist”, 63.

¹³ Cf. Brock, “A Hymn of St Ephrem on the Eucharist”, 64.

Church. He became famous through his writings, and his popularity prompted many later authors to publish their works in his name.

Ephrem lived in Nisibis in the early decades. There existed a mixed culture consisting of polytheism, Judaism, and several Christian denominations in Nisibis. The linguistic culture was also like the same, which is the ordinary means of communication was Aramaic and Greek and Latin were used as the administrative language. Therefore, it is necessary to know the specialties of the complex ethnicities before reading St Ephrem.

Mar Jacob, a signatory in the First Council of Nicaea (325 CE), was the bishop of Nisibis. Ephrem was doing his teaching ministry under him (later, this ministry gained him the title *The Founder of the School of Nisibis*). So it was Mar Jacob who gave diaconate to St Ephrem.

The sudden upheavals in the political scenario of that time caused a drastic change in the Life of St Ephrem. *The edict of Milan* legalized Christianity in the Roman Empire in 325. Still, the death of Emperor Constantine I and the inability of the successors to protect the Empire offered a golden opportunity to Shapur II of Persia to besiege Nisibis in 338 CE. So we come across the second phase of St Ephrem as a refugee in Edessa. All these political instabilities were well narrated poetically in *The Hymn of Nisibis*. He has compared this political situation with that of the Ark of Noah in the book of Genesis. Shapur again attacked the surrounding cities of Nisibis around 359 CE. Constantius II could not respond, and the campaign of Julian ended by witnessing his sorrowful death in 363. His successor Jovian was forced to surrender Nisibis to Persia, and it culminated with the expulsion of the entire Christian population to Persia. Therefore, the second phase of the Life of St Ephrem was spent in the school of Edessa, where Syriac, a dialect of Aramaic, was spoken. As stated above, he was also confronted by Arianism, Marcionism, Manichaeism, and several types of Gnostic teachings. He defended the Nicene orthodoxy through his hymns.

All the works of St Ephrem were not available, but around four hundred hymns are still preserved. Ephrem is a vantage point of many cultural heritages, such as Judaism, Greek Philosophy, and Mesopotamian tradition of symbols. The majority of his literary works are in lyrical form, and those lyrics are teaching hymns. The poetic scheme of Bardaisan might have influenced him, and he used the poetic form (*Madrashé*) to defend the Faith by devising the hymns with doctrines to make the Christians conscious about the heretic teaching.¹⁴ Apart from poetry, he used verse homilies (*more*) and biblical commentaries too.

As stated in the preceding paragraphs, St Ephrem used the poetic form to teach the catholic doctrines and implemented those hymns in the prayers.¹⁵ Therefore, the Syriac churches used the works of St Ephrem in the liturgy and canonical prayers. Moreover, since the zealous missionaries from the Persian Church did mission work in the far East, the St. Thomas Christians are also influenced by the teachings of St Ephrem directly and indirectly.

1.2. St Ephrem and the Syriac Christianity in the East

Christianity began in Jerusalem. Later it spread to other places, including Persia and Asia, and so on. Christianity in Nisibis and Edessa is generally known as Syriac Christianity because they celebrated the liturgy and wrote theology in the Syriac language. As if Greek and Latin, Syriac was also one of the main languages of early Christianity. As said in the introduction, Nisibis was under Roman Empire until the time of the Persian invasion. The edict of Milan granted religious freedom to Christians, and it is one of the reasons for spreading

¹⁴ “The Hymns Against Heresies employ colourful metaphors to describe the Incarnation of Christ as fully human and divine. Ephrem asserts that Christ's unity of humanity and divinity represents peace, perfection and salvation; in contrast, docetism and other heresies sought to divide or reduce Christ's nature and, in doing so, rend and devalue Christ's followers with their false teachings.” Cf. Paul S., *St Ephrem the Syrian and St Gregory the Theologian Confront the Aryans*, 7.

¹⁵ Cf. Dr. T. Paniker, “St Ephrem and the Eucharist”, 5.

Christian Faith in the place of the Roman Empire. The heretic influences were hazardous to the Catholic Faith of the Syriac Christians in Nisibis at the time of St Ephrem. Ephrem had to defend Faith from heresies like Gnosticism, Marcionism, and Manichaeism, and above all, from Arianism.

1.3. Syriac Literature at the time of St Ephrem

Syriac and Aramaic dialect has been adopted as the literary language of Aramaic speaking Christianity in the early centuries.¹⁶ There were many literary works in Syriac from the second to the twentieth century. This long period of Syriac literature can be divided into six periods for the convenience of analyzing the literary works by classifying the ascetic authors and other writers. The periods of Syriac literature are; a) the earliest literature (2 & 3 century), b) golden age of Syriac literature (4th C), c) fifth to mid-seventh century, d) mid-seventh to end of the thirteenth century, e) 14th – 19th century, and f) the 20th century. Due to the Arab invasion (7-20th C), the writers of the Syriac churches preferred (or were forced) to write Arabic rather than Syriac.¹⁷ Therefore, the Syriac Christian Scholars of the 19th century played a vital role in transcending Greek Philosophy and science to the Arab World. In this process, all those works in Greek were translated first to Syriac and then to Arabic. Later those works were

¹⁶ Cf. S. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature in Moran Etho-9* (Kottayam: SEERI, 1997) 7.

¹⁷ “Period D (7th -13th cent.) belongs to the time of the Omayyads (7th – 8th century), ‘Abbasids (750c.- 1100), Seljuks (in Turkey, 11th/12th centuries) and Mongols (from 13th century). Period E (14th -19th cent.) belongs to the time of (successively) Mongol, Mamluk (along with other local dynasties), and Ottoman rule in Western Asia, and opened with a time of great devastation and destruction through war and the Black Death. Period F (20th cent.) belongs to the time of the breakup of the Ottoman Empire and the emergence of the modern nation states in West Asia.” Cf. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac*, 10.

translated to Latin from Arabic. Therefore it is true that Syriac was a bridge in connecting Greek Philosophy to Western Europe.¹⁸

Here my concern of Syriac Literature rests upon the first two periods of the Syriac literature. First, the pre-Ephremic works including *the Diatessaron, the Old Syriac Gospels, works of Bardaisan, the Odes of Solomon, the Acts of Thomas, the Works attributed to Melito the Philosopher, the Syriac Sentences of Menander, the Letter of Mara, the Story of the Armaean Sage Ahikas* and so on.¹⁹ Among these early Syriac writings, the first five works are significant when we analyze the poetical works of St Ephrem. When the literary works of St Ephrem are analyzed, it is very evident that he was influenced by the writing style (writing in meter) of Bardaisan and the allusive character of the *Odes of Solomon*.

In the first two centuries, Baptism and the Eucharist theology were very strong, and the early Syriac Christianity was acquainted with Symbols and Imageries. Therefore, we find allusive language in the Syriac literature. The religious persecution and the life situation might have been the two prominent reasons for using this kind of allusive language in literature. The majority of the people were from an agricultural background and used to teach the doctrines of Faith, or they have used the same to escape from the persecutors and proclaim the gospels. This is what we see in the *Odes of Solomon*.

In the same way, Bardaisan of Edessa also spread the wrong teachings. He tried to interpret Christology by using the existing Astrology and Metaphysics and ended in heresy.²⁰ Even then, he contributed a poetic style to Syriac Literature (pentameter). He taught that the incarnation of Jesus Christ was to restore the

¹⁸ Cf. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature*, 11.

¹⁹ Cf. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature*, 14-18.

²⁰ Cf. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature*, 15.

disharmony of cosmic elements (fire, water, earth, and air). Apart from the heretic teachings of Bardaisan, Aryanism was also prevalent in society.

Another prominent theologian in Syriac literature was Aphraht (+145). His theology was based on Judaism. He lived in the interior parts of the Persian Empire. He owed 23 demonstrations in Syriac. These are some of the pre-Ephremic works in the Syriac literature.

1.3.1. Cultural Background

St Ephrem is a culmination of three cultures as Greek, Jewish, and Mesopotamian traditions.²¹ This triple heritage is visible in his writings. The Eucharistic metaphor *The Medicine of Life* is one of the prominent examples of the ancient Mesopotamian cultural influence.²² The imagery of *the Medicine of Life* refers to Jesus Christ and the Eucharist²³ in all the works of St Ephrem. Apart from the Mesopotamian culture, we can find the trace of Judaism. Many of the imageries were taken from the Old Testament (*The Hymn on Paradise* is one of the best examples.), and it shows that he used to refer Jewish Bible. Ephrem was also influenced by Greek culture. He was aware of the way of the theological thinking of the Greek Christians. These three cultural heritages are fine-tuned in the writings of St Ephrem.

1.3.2. St Ephrem's Influence and Contribution to Syriac Literature

St. Ephrem's influence on Syriac Literature is remarkable. He was a theologian who employed poetry as an expressive means to defend Faith.²⁴ He composed poetry in the form of 'Memra' and 'Madrasha'.²⁵ His approach to theology is

²¹ Cf. Paniker, "St Ephrem and the Eucharist" in *Aikya Samiksha*, 5.

²² Cf. S. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem* (Michigan: Cistercian Publications, 1992) 19-24.

²³ 'Your body is the Medicine of Life', Nisibis 76:6

²⁴ Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 160.

²⁵ "The *memra* is employed for narrative poetry, and is written in couplets consisting of 7+7 syllables (later known as the metre of Mar Ephrem), while the *madrasha* is used for lyric poetry

rooted in the Scripture, and the method he used for teaching theology was well accepted among the people of God. Ephrem uses many biblical images and symbols in his poems, from describing the Eucharistic Mysteries and the economy of salvation.²⁶ The fundamental doctrines of the Catholic Church were easily imprinted in the hearts of the people through his poetic style of heptasyllabic couplets. He made use of the imageries familiar to the people. Therefore they could associate the content of theology with that of the existing meaning of the imagery and thereby learn the exact meaning of the doctrine. For Example, St Ephrem explains the incarnation of the Second Person in the Holy Trinity and connects it with the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* in *Hymn on Nativity* as follows:

*Let Eve today rejoice in Sheol,
For her daughter's Son
It has come down as the Medicine of Life
To revive His mother's mother.*²⁷

His commentary on the *Diatessaron* deals with the interpretation of the *Diatessaron*. His other contributions to the Syriac literature are *Commentary on Acts*, *Commentary on the Pauline Epistles*, *Prose Refutations* (which includes five discourses addressed to Hypatius, against false doctrine, against Bardaisan, against Marcion, against Mani), *Discourse on Our Lord*, *Letters to Publius* (Eschatological teachings), *memre on Faith*, *Memre against Bardaisan*, *On Janah and the repentance of Nineveh*, *On the Sinful Woman*, *On Solitudes*, *Madrashé on Faith*, *Madrashé on Nisibis*, *Madrashé against Heresies* (Marcionism, Bardaisan, Mani, etc.), *Madrashé on Virginity*, *Madrashé on the*

written in stanzas, which can be in a variety of different syllabic metres, though for anyone poem the same meter is adhered to throughout.” Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature*, 23.

²⁶ Cf. Paniker, “St Ephrem and the Eucharist” in *Aikya Samiksha*, 5.

²⁷Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 99.

Church, Madrashe on Nativity, Madrashe on Unleavened Bread, Madrashe on Paradise, Madrashe on the Fast, Madrashe against Julian and so on.²⁸

Therefore, his writings remain always new and relevant to the postmodern world. There is no wonder in calling him the “Harp of the Holy Spirit” because the Holy Spirit inspires the saintly people to ruminate over the Scripture and seek the hidden treasures inside. St Ephrem became influential in the East and the West through his hymns, biblical interpretations, and theological discourses. When his literary works are analyzed, it becomes evident that he developed the Syriac literary style.

1.3.3. Eucharistic Images and Symbols in St Ephrem²⁹

The theology of St Ephrem is known as the theology of imageries and symbols. Symbols go beyond the usual way of thinking. It carries the reality. Ephrem was aware of the fact that symbols are part of human beings. Therefore, man can reach mystic experience through symbols. Since every symbol has a hidden nature, it must be appropriately interpreted. Here some of the Eucharistic symbols in St Ephrem’s literary works are analyzed. I will introduce some of the imagery here to avoid repeating those Eucharistic imageries in the third chapter. Moreover, it will help me to focus on the Eucharistic imagery of *the Medicine of Life*. Therefore, I will not expound the said imagery here, but I will briefly introduce the same.

The content of the title, “Eucharistic Images and Symbols in St Ephrem,” is prepared mainly from the findings from the book *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem* by Sebastian Brock. Brock has brilliantly picked out the Eucharistic imageries from the entire hymns of St Ephrem. It is necessary to get a glimpse over those Eucharistic Imageries. He has pointed out three primary Eucharistic metaphors in *The Luminous Eye*, such

²⁸ Cf. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature*, 23-28.

²⁹ Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 99-114.

as “*The Medicine of Life*³⁰,” “The Coal of Fire,³¹” and “The Pearl³².” These three imageries will be discussed here in detail to develop the succeeding chapters.

a. *The Medicine of Life:* Medicine of Life is the key imagery of my dissertation. By interpreting this imagery, I'll probe the fact that religious language can transcend the people's minds to divine revelation entire store by using this set imagery sent a frame proves that Jesus Christ is *the Medicine of Life*. St Ephrem has come to this conclusion as a result of his deep meditation of the Holy Scriptures and the teachings of the Church. He has been influenced a lot by the Gospel of John. I explain it in the third chapter. Apart from this, he uses many Old Testament incidents to define the meaning of the Eucharistic imagery, *the Medicine of Life*. For example, “Moses hid the symbol of Christ as a *Medicine of Life* in the unleavened bread.” He gradually develops the idea of *the Medicine of Life* by selectively taking the Old Testament episodes.

b. *The Coal of Fire:* Ephrem employs the metaphor ‘the coal of fire’ to represent the Eucharist. This imagery is taken from the Prophets (Isaiah 6:6). Ephrem says that all the Christians hold and consume Christ, the new Coal of Fire. The same imagery is used in the Holy Qurbano of the Syro-Malankara Catholic Church. When the Holy Eucharist has distributed, the priest prays, “The Coal of Fire, which is Your Body and Blood, is given to the true faithful.” It shows how Ephrem’s theology influenced the Catholic Church later.³³

³⁰ Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 99.

³¹ Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 103.

³² Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 106.

³³ “In Your Bread, Lord. there is hidden the Spirit who is not consumed, in Your Wine there dwells the Fire that is not drunk: The Spirit is in Your Bread. the Fire in Your Wine, a manifest wonder, that our lips have received.” (Faith 10:8) Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 104.

- c. The Pearl:** Ephrem's poems on the pearl is also an indirect indication of the Eucharist. He says in a poem that he took a pearl into his hands and in that he watched the symbols which revealed the images of the Kingdom and the glory of God. That pearl became a fountain from which he drank the mysteries of the Son.³⁴ Ephrem presents the pearl as the Eucharist symbolically.
- d. Bread of Life:** He compares the unleavened Bread of the Passover as a symbol of the Bread of Life, representing the Eucharist.³⁵ In this way, St Ephrem has used the Passover celebration to illustrate the parallelism between the Eucharist and the Old Testament unleavened bread.
- e. Paschal Lamb**

The most important imagery of the Eucharist used by St Ephrem is the Paschal lamb. The Last Supper is the meeting point of the Old Testament Lamb and the True lamb. It indicates that Eucharist is the continuation of the Last Supper and the sacrifice on the Cross. Therefore, the Eucharistic celebration in the Church makes presents the paschal mystery.

1.4. Conclusion

The theological disquisitions of St Ephrem are augmented with imageries, symbols, and metaphors. He extensively used many root metaphors such as physician, mirror, and *Medicine of Life*, and so on. He made use of many symbols and imageries to bring out the theology of the Eucharist. His brilliant implementation of Old Testament imageries to the New Testament paschal mysteries was enough to prove that Jesus continues in the world and gives Himself through the Holy Eucharist. To prove that, he makes use of the imageries like 'the Coal of Fire,' 'the Pascal Lamb,' 'the Pearl,' 'the *Medicine*

³⁴ Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 106.

³⁵ "It was the very same Christ in the Upper Room, who gave and was distributed to all." Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 102.

of Life,' and so on. For Ephrem, there is a connection between incarnation and Eucharist. Eucharist is the extension of incarnation. The fruit of incarnation is salvation, and that is experienced through the Eucharist.

The proper analysis of the historical background clarifies that the community where he lived was influenced by the heretic teachings, as explained. This means that the people were affected/confused by the false *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts* of the heretic teachers of the time. To defend these heretic FNCs, St Ephrem gives maximum possible clarification to the Catholic teachings of the Economy of Salvation by incorporating the Old Testament events from the post-resurrection perspective. He tried to elevate the Faith of the people to the right track. As a zealous missionary, he wanted to protect the Faith of the people. Therefore, he used the symbols and imageries familiar to the people, which enabled him to express the actual teachings of the Christian faith. At the same time, it cannot be neglected that the political situation was also not favorable to him in expressing theology directly because Christians were under persecution in the Persian Empire at his time and even later.

The introductory chapter aims to prepare the ground for providing the reasons for the transcendental leap of the Eucharistic imagery *the Medicine of Life*. The introductory chapter clarifies that theology is the response of the time to the Faith seeking of the people. Therefore the language of the theology is decided by the context in which it is introduced. That means all the FNCs make a kind of mutation in the *Neuro Context* of the person based on how he and she approach the available *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts*. Therefore, the proper formation of the euro context is very significant in the semantic shift (transcending leap). Thus, the transcendental leap of the said imagery is highly dependent on the context. The way the same imagery is used from time to time will be discussed in the succeeding chapters.

CHAPTER TWO

MEDICINE OF LIFE AND THE CHURCH

2.1. Introduction

The law of prayer is the law of Faith³⁶ for the Eastern Churches. From the general introduction and the first chapter, it was clear that the Life of St Ephrem was self-explanatory proof for the same mandate. Liturgy is the primary and official way of celebrating the salvific mysteries in the Church. Understanding what a community believes becomes very easy by analyzing the liturgy. This is the primary mode of preserving and transmitting the essentials of Faith. If it is the case, it is necessary to do a detailed search into the roots to find out the meanings of the imagery of *the Medicine of Life*. In this chapter, I am examining the meaning of the imagery of *the Medicine of Life*. I will not try to associate this imagery with Eucharist directly where as I am trying to trace the different levels of the meaning of the said imagery.

The general conclusion must deal with the transcendental leap of the Medicine of Life's imagery as Eucharistic imagery. The concept '*Medicine of Life*' has been used differently in the Church from the very beginning of its origin. This chapter focuses primarily on the imagery of "*the Medicine of Life*" to find out its sources and its use in the liturgy. I have referred to the liturgy of the Malankara Catholic Church for this purpose. This chapter is significant in analyzing the transcendental leap of the imagery '*the Medicine of Life*.' The search for the use of the said imagery in the culture, Scripture, and liturgy will include different aspects of the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* by which the salvific mystery is presented. This imagery is the cultural product of the time. *Therefore, medicine of Life* is imagery with different layers of meaning.

The first meaning that comes to our mind is medicine that cures physical and psychological illness and nurtures a human person. But here, this imagery has transcended the said levels of meaning. When a word or phrase or sentence

³⁶ [Lex orandi, lex credendi - Wikipedia](#)

transcends its primary meaning and attains an abstract dimension known as semantic shift (suggestiveness), because, in suggestiveness, the actual existence of reality is not necessary, for example, When the meaning of the phrase “A Village on the Gages” is analyzed, the following meanings will be derived out of the same such as ‘A village situates on the bank of the river Ganges,’ ‘A village near to the River Ganges,’ and finally ‘A prosperous village.’ Here the third level of meaning is the suggestive meaning. Even though the same semantic expansion occurs in the transcendental leap, both suggestiveness and the transcendental leap are slightly different. In the latter case, the reality is necessary, whereas suggestiveness does not demand the same. The imagery of ‘*the Medicine of Life*’ connects us to the existing fact though the accidents remain here. It brings us to the depth of reality. This chapter studies the different uses of the said imagery in liturgical prayers, sacraments, and the teachings of the Fathers of the Church to analyze its transcendental leap. To explore the transcendental leap of the Eucharistic imagery ‘*the Medicine of Life*,’ the cultural, biblical, and patristic influences must be studied along with the proper scrutiny of the liturgical texts of the Malankara Syrian Catholic Church to find out the semantic expansion.

2.2. Cultural Influence

The search for immortality is there in the minds of all people on the earth. Every culture brings its own stories of elixirs that provide immortality. Here I am explaining how the concept of Medicine of Life existed in the culture where St Ephrem lived. As I stated, medicine is part of the human community. Various types of medicinal practices have existed across the world. There are physical, psychological, and spiritual therapies. These branches have different sub-branches and multiple dimensions in accordance with their use. Here, the discussion is on the imagery of *Medicine of Life* that existed in the Semitic, Egyptian, and Mesopotamian cultures. The reason for focusing on the Middle East terrain is that St Ephrem was exposed to these three cultures. Among the

said cultures, the concept of *Medicine of Life* is taken from Mesopotamian Medicine.

Mesopotamian Medicine is predominantly based on supernatural concepts, although rudimentary traces of empiric medicine are discernible, whereas, in Greek culture, systematic medical practices existed. It is written in Hammurabi's Code that if a healer causes a highborn person blindness or death, both hands of the healer will be cut off.³⁷ It is to show the concern that was given to medicine and its uses. To be specific, medicine should grant Life and health. It means that even at the time of Babylonian exile, the practice of medicine was there in the Middle East. At the time of St Ephrem, the medical techniques might have improved. St. Ephrem might have used this medicine concept to present the Eucharistic reality with the imagery of '*the Medicine of Life*.' That means he made use of the said imagery to expand the meaning of the Eucharist. Ephrem has taken the healing aspect of medicine to interpret the Holy Eucharist. Now I will explain the biblical dimensions of the said imagery.

2.3. Biblical Influence

The hymns and sermons of St Ephrem were filled with Biblical imageries and symbols. Here we would be analyzing the imageries of *Medicine of Life* in the light of the Holy Bible. It is helpful to know how the meaning of the cultural product changes with the application of the divine revelation. The Bible is indeed written by using the symbols and imageries of the cultures to which the People of God were exposed. In other words, the human authors of the Sacred Scriptures might have interpreted the divine revelation within the limitations of the human language (better to say NC). Therefore, the gradation of revelation is very evident in the Bible. All the events in the Old Testament are perfected in the New Testament because the New Testament authors have interpreted Old

³⁷ Cf. Retief, F.P., and L. Cilliers. "Mesopotamian Medicine.", 3.

Testament from the Resurrection Experience under the guidance of the Holy Spirit through divine inspiration.

The imagery of *Medicine of Life* has been directed towards two meanings in the Bible; a) Medicine that gives Life and b) Medicine that is possessed by Life (here the Life is personified). It means that here both ‘medicine’ and ‘Life’ stand for Jesus Christ. We will come to this point in the next chapter. The imagery of *Medicine of Life* is present in the Holy Bible from Genesis to Revelation directly or indirectly. The concept of Medicine of Life is visible in many of the incidents in the Old Testament. Those indirect indications are given below.

- a. **Creation** (Gen. 1&2, 1-2): Creation is the result of the love of the Triune God. God created the human being in His image and likeness and gave Life, and thereby man participated in the divine Life. St Ephrem explains it with the imagery of ‘the robe of Glory’ in his hymn on *Paradise*. The story of creation is the recollection of the writer of the Sacred Scripture about the glorious state of man. The story of creation conveys the message that the incarnation of Jesus Christ is the result of God's Love towards humanity.
- b. **Sin and Promise** (Gen.3, 2-3): The fall of man resulted in the loss of the divine Life. Here, God reveals the economy of salvation to humankind that He will send the savior to redeem man from the clutches of the consequences of his great fall and ensure divine life.
- c. **The Great Flood** (Gen.7, 6): The story of the great flood also deals with a new creation and a level of new Life. Here the ‘great flood’ can broadly be considered ‘medicine of life’ because it purified the society.
- d. **Aaron’s Miraculous Rod** (Ex.7:8, 55): Aaron’s miraculous staff turned into snakes and swallowed all other snakes of the Pharaoh’s scorers. It also symbolizes Jesus Christ.
- e. **Bread from Heaven** (Ex.16, 62): The Israelites were given bread from heaven, nourishing them with the same. It revitalized them to continue their

Exodus. Here also, we can see the indications of the imagery ‘*the Medicine of Life.*’

- f. Bitter water made sweet** (Ex.15, 62): The people were thirsty, and they were at the brim of death. At this time, the bitter water turned to sweet became an elixir of Life for them.
- g. Water from the Rock** (Ex.17, 64): This was similar to the abovementioned incident. In this case, also water became a medicine of Life.
- h. The Decalogue** (Ex.20, 66): The Decalogue was also *the Medicine of Life*. It consists of the commandment of God. Therefore, the Decalogue is also *the Medicine of Life*.
- i. The Blood of the Covenant** (Ex.24, 70): With the blood of the covenant, the Lord made the covenant with Moses. It symbolizes the blood of Jesus, and therefore it also stands for *the Medicine of Life*.
- j. The Ark of the Covenant** (Ex.25:10-22, 71): The Ark also symbolizes *the Medicine of Life*.

Here I have selected a few incidents from the Bible which turned to imageries later in the prayers of the people of God. Then, in the third chapter, we will see how these indirect indications of Medicine of Life are used in St Ephrem. Now the direct quotes are given below.

- a. “A cheerful heart is a good medicine”(Proverb 17:22)
- b. “There is no one to uphold your cause, no medicine for your wound, no healing for you.”(Jeremiah 30:17)
- c. “Go up to Gilead and take balm, O virgin daughter Egypt! In vain you have used many medicines: there is no healing for you.”(Jeremiah 46:11, 918)
- d. “...For its gall, heart, and liver are useful as medicine.”(Tobit 6:5, 449)
- e. “Faithful friends are life-saving medicine.”(Sirach 6:16)

The biblical usages above show that the scripture writers have hardly used the primary meaning of ‘medicine,’ whereas its symbolic meanings are prioritized.

For example, “Faithful friends are life-saving medicine.”(Sirach 6:16) Here the ‘faithful friends’ are identified with the ‘life-saving medicine.’ Therefore, the use of the symbolic dimension of a word was prevalent when the Old Testament books were written down.

2.4. Patristic View on *Medicine of Life*

We do not find any direct mention of the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* as imagery of the Holy Eucharist in the writings of the Fathers of the Church. They lived before St Ephrem except for St Ignatius of Antioch. According to St Ignatius of Antioch, the Eucharist is the Medicine of Immortality,³⁸ but for St Ephrem, it is *the Medicine of Life*. Ephrem presents even the incarnation itself as *the Medicine of Life*. (Hymns on Nativity 13:2)³⁹ According to St Ephrem, Christ came as a physician, and he was with three medicines such as the Bread, Wine, and Chrism. (Hymns on Virginitly 37:3)⁴⁰

2.5. Use of the Imagery *Medicine of Life* in Malankara Liturgy

The imagery of *Medicine of Life* is used in the Malankara Liturgy. Every liturgical service will be analyzed in detail to determine the use of the said imagery. The theology of the Syriac Fathers influences all the prayers in the Malankara Liturgy. I have chosen this section to prove that even now, we are exploring the theological richness of the teachings of the Syriac Fathers. It also shows how we are connected to the FNCs of the Fathers of the Church. I try to analyze how the concept ‘the Medicine of Life’ is presented here.

³⁸Cf. T. Paniker, “St Ephrem and the Eucharist”, 8.

³⁹Cf. T. Paniker, “St Ephrem and the Eucharist”, 8.

⁴⁰Cf. T. Paniker, “St Ephrem and the Eucharist”, 8.

2.5.1. Qurbono

The medicine of life' imagery highly influences the Order of the Holy Qurbono of SMCC. Here the voice of the Lord is *the Medicine of Life* that brings the dead to Life.⁴¹ The purpose of medicine is to give Life by rejuvenating a human person physically and psychologically. Still, the concept of medicine has another dimension of meaning: the rejuvenation of the soul. Therefore, all that gives Life or rejuvenates Life is *the Medicine of Life*. Here some of the rambling thoughts on the said imagery are given below.

- a. **Life-Giving Word:** Jesus Christ is presented as the life-giving word in the Anaphora of Jacob.⁴² How does Jesus become the life-giving word? The incarnation and resurrection of our Lord Jesus Christ is the answer. The same theology is presented with the Eucharistic imagery 'the medicine of life' in St Ephrem.
- b. **Life-giving washing:** All the filth accumulated in the soul will be removed with the life-giving washing by Jesus Christ (Anaphora of Jacob).⁴³ The Holy Eucharist itself is the Medicine of Life that provides life-giving washing. It leads to a spiritual catharsis.
- c. **Life-Giving Bread:** The consecrated Bread and wine become the sources of Life. The transubstantiation of the same will be taking place with the hovering of the Holy Spirit.⁴⁴ Therefore it is advised to take part in the life-giving body and the blood.⁴⁵

⁴¹Cf. *The Order of the Holy Qurbono of SMCC* (Trivandrum: The Major Archiepiscopal Curia, 2015) 18.

⁴² Cf. *The Order of the Holy Qurbono of SMCC*, 26, 27, 34, 44-46.

⁴³ Cf. *The Order of the Holy Qurbono of SMCC*, 39.

⁴⁴ Cf. *The Order of the Holy Qurbono of SMCC*, 54.

⁴⁵ Cf. *The Order of the Holy Qurbono of SMCC*, Anaphora of St Jacob 65, 68-69, St. John 95-96, Bishop Mar Dynisius 142-143, 155, Mar Ivanios 165-166, St. Peter 188-189, Mar Kusthos, the Patriarch of Rome 210-211.

- d. Source of Eternal Life:** Eucharist is defined as the source of eternal Life (Anaphora of Jacob).⁴⁶ It is another dimension of the Medicine of Life that is Jesus Christ.
- e. Life-giving passion:** (Anaphora of St John.) We attain Life by the passion of our Lord Jesus Christ.⁴⁷ Medicine is made through a different process of crushing and mixing. Jesus is the Medicine of Life because he became such medicine to us by his passion and resurrection. Passion was not necessary for Jesus to be the Medicine of Life, but we needed to realize the value of the medicine that he brought to us. For through his passion, he showed how much he loved us. Therefore the Eucharist is the life-giving divine mystery.⁴⁸
- f. Life-giving death:** One gets Life in Christ when he lives holy. Eternity is attained, thereby death in Christ. (Anaphora of Mar Osthathios of Antioch)⁴⁹
- g. Sanctifying Sacrifice:** It is prayed in the Holy Qurbono to purify the one who takes part in the Holy Mass with the sanctifying grace dispensed in the Holy Eucharist (St Father's Mkanashtha Order).⁵⁰

2.5.2. Canonical Prayers

All the individual Churches in the Catholic Church and the Orthodox Churches have canonical prayers. The canonical prayers are the official prayers of the Church. These prayers are deeply rooted in the Holy Scriptures and the teachings of the Fathers of the Church. The primary aims of these prayers are to teach the dogmas of the Church to prevent the heretical teachings of the time

⁴⁶ Cf. *The Order of the Holy Qurbono of SMCC*, 72, 73.

⁴⁷ Cf. *The Order of the Holy Qurbono of SMCC*, 91.

⁴⁸ Cf. *The Order of the Holy Qurbono of SMCC*, 93.

⁴⁹ Cf. *The Order of the Holy Qurbono of SMCC*, 219, 234, 235.

⁵⁰ Cf. *The Order of the Holy Qurbono of SMCC*, 241.

and at the same time for the sanctification of the hours. Therefore, people will learn the dogmatic teachings of the Church when they pray canonical or any other liturgical prayers. There are two types of canonical prayers in the West Syrian Ecclesial Tradition; a) *Penkisa* and b) *Sheemo* (Canonical prayers for ordinary days). Since the translation of *Penkisa* is not available, *Sheemo* is used here for referring *The* canonical prayers of the Syro Malankara Catholic Church are divided into seven canonical hours, such as *Ramso*(Vespers- 6 pm), *Suthoro*(Compline- 9 pm), *Liliyo*(Matins & Lauds- 3 am), *Sapro*(Prime- 6 am), *Thos Soin*(Terce- 9 am), *Sheth Shoin*(Sext- 12 pm)and *Tsha Shoin*(None- 3 pm). Though *Sheemo* symbolizes the agricultural situation (This interpretation is made by Patriarch Mar Ignatius Bar Vahib of the 12th century.), its suggestiveness gets its perfection in the Paschal Mystery of Jesus Christ.⁵¹The main thrust of this section in this thesis is to find out whether there is any imagery that represents Eucharist in terms of Medicine of Life and analyze the other sacraments and salvific mysteries to which the imagery *Medicine of Life* is referred.

There are many prayers in the canonical prayers in which the faithful prays to Jesus to make them alive out of death.⁵²In addition, there are various imageries used to portray the importance of *the Medicine of Life*. The following are some examples.

a) Jesus as *the Medicine of Life*⁵³

The *Qolo I* of the prime on Tuesday (*Subho*) conveys that Jesus is *the Medicine of Life*. Here it is prayed that the Samaritan woman was reluctant in proving water to Jesus because there is no *Medicine of Life* in that water carried by that

⁵¹Cf. *Sheemo* (Pattom: The Major Archiepiscopal Curia of the Syro Malankara Catholic Church) iii.

⁵²Cf. *Sheemo*, 23.

⁵³Cf. *Sheemo*, 102.

woman. In contrast, Jesus has given her the source of *the Medicine of Life*. And the prayer further explains it (water) as the blood of Jesus. It means that there is a direct indication of the Eucharist in the said prayer.

b) Eucharist as Tree of Life

In Tuesday, Prime, *Qolo II*,⁵⁴ Eucharist is interpreted as *Tree of Life* with the explanation of the incident of the thief who was crucified at the right hand of Jesus. It is instructed to observe vigilance and fasting for receiving the fruits of the *Tree of Life*. This tree of Life is Jesus himself, who was crucified on the Cross. The Cross also symbolizes the risen Christ. The prayer states that the Cross is the Tree of Life that grants us the fruit of the resurrection of Christ. A tree that gives death and curse completely turns to the source of life and grace through the paschal mysteries.

c) Eucharist as the life-giving water

In the *Qolo (Subho, Wednesday, 6th Hour)*,⁵⁵ St Mary is compared to the tabernacle founded by Moses because she bears Jesus, who is the life-giving water in her womb. When the Israelites were about to die, Moses struck the rock, and water came out of it, and it was life-giving water for them. The divine intervention through the Holy Spirit enabled Mother Mary to bear Jesus, the life-giving water. This *Qolo* represents Mary as the tabernacle. The Eucharistic presence of Jesus is sacredly kept in the tabernacle. Therefore, this *Qolo* has a

⁵⁴ Cf. *Sheemo*, 107

⁵⁵ Cf. *Sheemo*, 149.

Eucharistic dimension. It also indicates that the incarnation of Jesus itself is a medicine of Life.

d) Eucharist as Elixir of Life⁵⁶

The tenth stanza of the II *Qolo* of the vespers of Thursday conveys the message that those who eat and drink the Body and Blood of the savior will live after death. It is a direct indication of the Eucharist as Medicine of Life.

2.5.3. Perunnal Kramam

The *Perunnal Kramam* of the Syro-Malankara Catholic Church uses the word “Life” in many prayers of the Major Feasts. Here I try to find out the similar imageries of the imagery of *the Medicine of Life*.

- a. The voice of the Lord:** The voice of the Lord is defined as the life-giving voice in one of the prayers of the *Yelda*.⁵⁷The imagery ‘the voice of the Lord’ suggests the meaning of the imagery ‘*the Medicine of Life*.’ As if the medicine is used for curing the sick person, the voice of the Lord gives life to the people.
- b. Dew of Life:** In the prayer of the *Yelda*, it is prayed that let the dew of Life be showered upon the dead in the lamenting abode of Hades.⁵⁸This indicates that the nativity of Jesus brings hope to the demised people. Here the imagery of the dew of Life resembles the imagery of *the Medicine of Life*.

⁵⁶ Cf. *Sheemo*, Subho, Thursday, Prime, *Qolo II*, 156., Menolam, Monday, Ramsa, 253. Wednesday,

Lilio Qolo II, 355. Thursday, Prime, Qolo, 381.

⁵⁷ Cf. The Synodal Commission for Liturgy, *Perunnalukal*, Yalda (Trivandrum: The Major Archiepiscopal Curia) 16.

⁵⁸ Cf. *Perunnalukal*, 18.

- c. Life-Giving Cross:** In the prayers of the *Sleeba Akhosham*, in the prayers of every feat, the Cross is identified as a life-giving one because Jesus was crucified on the Cross.⁵⁹Therefore the Cross symbolizes the Risen Jesus. Moreover, the Cross heals our wounds.⁶⁰
- d. Life-Giving Water:** In one of the prayers of the *Denha*, Jesus is identified as the life-giving water from the rock.⁶¹ The event from the Exodus influences this prayer. In the prayers of *Vade Dalmeede*, it is advised to accompany the life-giving water.⁶²

2.5.4. Prumion & Sedhara

The incarnation of Jesus Christ is considered as life-giving medicine. The incarnation is for the rejuvenation of humankind. Therefore the priest prays, “Protect us, who eat your body and your blood with your seal of life.”⁶³The people of God are given a new life with the death of Christ.⁶⁴The passion itself is considered life-giving, and therefore the priest prays that the passion of Jesus Christ may wash away the trespasses and sins from the people of God.⁶⁵The commandment given at the Last Supper is the Pleroma of the salvific history because his commandment is life-giving, and at the same time, it stands for the Eucharist.⁶⁶The entire content of the Prumion Sedra consists of the salvific mystery of our Lord Jesus Christ.

⁵⁹Cf. *Perunnalukal*, 79

⁶⁰Cf. *Perunnalukal*, 32.

⁶¹Cf. *Perunnalukal*, 95.

⁶²Cf. *Perunnalukal*, 177.

⁶³Cf. *Perunnalukal*, 21

⁶⁴Cf. *Perunnalukal*, 7.

⁶⁵Cf. The synodal Commission for Liturgy, *Hasa Azhchayile Prumion Sedra* (Trivandrum: The Major Archiepiscopal Curia, 2018) 9,11,17,26,41.

⁶⁶Cf. *Hasa Azhchayile Prumion Sedra*, 48.

2.5.5. Sacraments

- a. **Baptism:** Baptism grants new Life in Christ. As if medicine gives rejuvenation to the body, through Baptism, one is born in Christ.⁶⁷ Jesus, the one who sanctifies the Seraphs, purified the water with his Baptism, and thereby the Children of Adam lived again in water and Spirit.⁶⁸ As if medicine cleanses the body and grants new Life, through Baptism, one is born in Christ.
- b. **Anointing of the Sick:** Forgiveness of sins is indirectly considered as *Medicine of Life* in the prayers of the Anointing of the Sick⁶⁹ and at the same time the forgiveness directed towards Jesus Christ (James 5:15,16). Sin persecutes the soul as if infirmity to the body. Therefore it is requested to Jesus to provide an apt medicine for the same.⁷⁰ Here both the doctor and Medicine are Jesus Christ.⁷¹
- c. **Funeral:** It is prayed that Jesus would give Life to those who have died with the Faith of Resurrection in Christ.⁷² The resurrection of our Lord Jesus Christ is presented as *the Medicine of Life*. Jesus promises that those who received the Holy Eucharist with Faith would receive eternal life.⁷³ The second coming of Christ gives life to the dead as if medicine brings back one from the mortal infirmity.⁷⁴

⁶⁷ Cf. The Synodal Commission for Liturgy, *Koodashsakal* (Trivandrum: The Major Archiepiscopal Curia, 2015) 7.

⁶⁸ Cf. *Koodashsakal*, 9.

⁶⁹ Cf. *Koodashsakal*, 93.

⁷⁰ Cf. *Koodashsakal*, 97.

⁷¹ Cf. *Koodashsakal*, 97.

⁷² Cf. *Koodashsakal*, 104.

⁷³ Cf. *Koodashsakal*, 162.

⁷⁴ Cf. *Koodashsakal*, 169.

2.6. Conclusion

The imagery '*the Medicine of Life*' is used with different dimensions of meaning in the Bible, in the teachings of the Fathers of the Church, the Holy *Qurbono* text, and the other liturgical texts of the Syro Malankara Catholic Church. When all these aspects are examined closely, it is clear that all those meanings are directed towards different levels of the Paschal Mystery of Jesus Christ and specific to Jesus Christ. The Eucharist is the commemoration of the Paschal Mystery of Jesus Christ. If it is so, all those said aspects of meaning focus on the Eucharistic Mystery. Each episode in the Paschal Mystery of Jesus Christ is meditated upon daily and prayed conscientiously daily. Therefore, it is helpful for the faithful to ruminate over the actual teachings of the Church and to take part in the Holy *Qurbono* sincerely. St Ephrem's theology has influenced the Antiochean Liturgy. It is very evident from this Chapter that St Ephrem's use of the imagery '*the Medicine of Life*' to indicate the Eucharist is highly influenced by the Bible. His narrative style has a resemblance with that of the evangelist St John. St John's Gospel influenced St Ephrem in composing the hymns will be dealt with in detail with comparative analysis in the succeeding chapter. So in the First Chapter, the historical background of the imagery '*the Medicine of Life*' is analyzed, and I am persuaded that this chapter granted a great perspective on how this imagery is presented in the Bible and used in the liturgy of the Malankara Catholic Church. The primary purpose of this chapter was to facilitate the study of the Transcendental Leap of the Eucharistic imagery, *the Medicine of Life*. It is evident from this chapter that all the direct and indirect use of the concept in the Medicine of Life indicates to Jesus Christ and the economy of salvation. Since the Holy Scriptures highly influenced St Ephrem, the said concept has got the Eucharistic dimension to show that Jesus is continuously present in the Church and to our naked eyes

through the Eucharistic presence. How does St Ephrem interpret Eucharist? What was the highest possible interpretation given to the Eucharist by St Ephrem? These questions are the focal point of the next chapter. The following chapter will discuss the transcendental leap of the imagery 'the Medicine of Life' and how this semantic leap transpires.

CHAPTER THREE

ST. EPHREM'S VISION OF *MEDICINE OF LIFE*

3.1. Introduction

St Ephrem has defined the transcendental and transubstantial nature of the Holy Eucharist by using various symbols. The world view of his time might have influenced him a lot in composing poems on divine mysteries by using the full potential of imageries. These imageries were taken from the Scripture and the culture. Human Ascend, the Robe of Glory, *the Medicine of Life*, the coal of fire, the pearl, the bridal chamber of the heart, and so on are prominent imageries used frequently by St Ephrem in his hymns, biblical interpretations, and sermons.⁷⁵ Among these imageries, “*The Medicine of Life*” is vital because he has repeatedly used this imagery to signify the Holy Eucharist. The concluding chapter focuses on extracting the different dimensions of the Eucharistic imagery of *the Medicine of Life*. It substantiates how the said imagery is used to express the mystery of Eucharist directly indirectly. Apart from this, the modus operandi of a transcendental leap of the said Eucharistic imagery will also be probed.

3.2. The Use of the Imagery *Medicine of Life*

The use of the imageries is constructive in associating abstract ideas. Since imageries are the subject of human senses and imagination, transferring the transcendental meaning becomes effective. That may be the reason why St Ephrem has chosen images to interpret the divine realities. St Ephrem wants to communicate that Jesus Christ, born of the Virgin Mary, suffered, died, and resurrected is *the Medicine of Life*. And this Medicine of Life is presented in the Holy Eucharist. St Ephrem was very good at handling the collective neuro context by using the available fragmentary neuro contexts. To prove that Jesus is the fulfillment of all he prophesies in the Old Testament, he brilliantly uses

⁷⁵Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye The Spiritual Vision of St Ephrem*, 12.

many incidents from the Old Testament. He uses them as imageries to represent the Holy Eucharist. He says that Moses had hidden the symbol of Christ as *Medicine of Life* in the *Unleavened Bread*⁷⁶

The same concept of the hidden *Medicine of Life* is also recurring in many of his worlds, such as Hymns on Nativity, Virginity, Paradise, etc.

3.2.1. Old Testament References

St Ephrem uses many Old Testament incidents, directly and indirectly, to substantiate that Jesus Christ fulfills all the prophecies of the Old Testament. His comparative study is not merely confined within the prophecies alone. He takes each incident from the Old Testament and proves logically how Jesus becomes the Pleroma. He says in “The Hymns on the Unleavened Bread” that those who have eaten from the unleavened bread have demised, whereas the people who received bread from the life-giver attained eternal Life.⁷⁷ He again says that the Church gives the living bread instead of the unleavened provided by Egypt. He compared Mary to Eve. According to him, Mary gave humanity the life-giving Bread rather than Eve’s deadly bread.

*Let the sixth day praise the one who created Adam on Friday. The evil one deceived him by mixing poison in his food. Whereas Jesus, through His incarnation, dispensed the Medicine of Life to both of them, and thereby man became alive.*⁷⁸

The careful analysis of the hymn given above proves that St Ephrem has made use of all his poetic skills in synthesizing the fall of Adam to justify the

⁷⁶“A.: χ≅ □ ≅ Ak□}N □χO} μγ

□≅AX P□ωθ □.:δ} ≅□□≅” Cf. J. E. Walters, *Ephrem the Syrian’s Hymns on the Unleavened Bread*, (USA: Gorgias Press, 2012), 18:15.

⁷⁷Cf. Paniker. "St Ephrem and the Eucharist.",6.

⁷⁸ G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Manushyavathara Geethangal*, Hymn no 26:9(Kottaym: OIRSI, 2001) 159.

incarnation of Jesus Christ. Like this, he makes use of many Old Testament references in his poetical works.

3.2.2. Mercy

St Ephrem uses the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* to portray the aspect of Divine Mercy. He says that the fountain of Life was hidden in Jesus, and it was given to all those who search for him.⁷⁹ Jesus gave his own body to the people to make them alive eternally.⁸⁰ St Ephrem proves that *the Medicine of Life* is Jesus Christ himself. The fallen man cannot attain the lost grace by his effort. Therefore, the Second Person in the Trinity was incarnated to bring the mercy of the Father to the entire people. It means that *the Medicine of Life* included the incarnation, passion, death, resurrection, and the second coming of Christ. It means that the eschatological aspect is also included in the term ‘Medicine of Life.’

3.2.3. Purification

St Ephrem uses the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* mainly for the Eucharist. But, apart from the same, the said imagery suggests many other meanings related to the Eucharist effects. One is purification. Medicine purifies the body; likewise, the Medicine of Life sanctifies the soul.⁸¹ Therefore St Ephrem teaches that the incarnation of Jesus is our purification, His Baptism is the absolution of our sins and His death is our Life.

3.2.4. Tree of Eden

Ephrem makes use of the ‘Tree of Eden’ to bring meaning to *the Medicine of Life*. He says that man was given a second chance to eat from the Tree of Life

⁷⁹ “He became thirsty and asked for water. But the fountain of Life that gives life to all was hidden in him.(Translation: Own)” Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, Hymn no 13:10(Kottaym: OIRSI, 2009) 26.

⁸⁰ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 28.

⁸¹ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 77.

through the birth, death, and resurrection of Christ.⁸²He also says that the dove that Noah sent took a rest in the tree of Life and rejuvenated with new Life.⁸³He also says that the fruit of the Tree of Life symbolizes the Body of Christ (Eucharist), which imparts life to those who eat from it. It means that St Ephrem uses the tree of Life as the symbol of the Eucharist (or Jesus Christ Himself).⁸⁴That is why he says that the tree of Life brought hope to the mortals.

3.2.5. Crucifixion

Medicine of Life and the crucifixion of Jesus are presented interconnected in the poetical works of St Ephrem. According to him, “Jesus has hidden the eternal life. Therefore, the lifeless death could swallow the One with Life. The fragrance of his life filled in the hades and therefore the hades vomited him.”(Own Translation)⁸⁵Here Ephrem has presented the death and resurrection of our Lord Jesus. Ephrem says that the Cross in which Jesus was crucified is life-giving, and therefore he continues and says, “The head of the Child upon which the life-giving sign of the cross is marked is blessed!”⁸⁶It indicates Baptism and confirmation. Through this sacrament, one becomes eligible to receive the Eucharist, *the Medicine of Life*.

In the ‘hymns on the incarnation,’ he explains symbolically how Jesus Christ, *the Medicine of Life*, was resurrected. He says that in the hades, the death opened its mouth widely and swallowed the body of Jesus, but *the Medicine of Life* hidden within the body was sprouted.⁸⁷In the Nissibian Hymns, he continues his

⁸² Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Kanyathva Geethangal*, Karthrupratheekangal, Hymn no 8:5(Kottaym: OIRSI, 2001) 51.

⁸³ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Kanyathva Geethangal*, 61.

⁸⁴ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Kanyathva Geethangal*, 10.

⁸⁵Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 33.

⁸⁶ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Kanyathva Geethangal*, 100.

⁸⁷ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Manushyavathara Geethangal*, (Kottaym: OIRSI, 2001) 41.

teachings and explains that *the Medicine of Life* gave Life to the dead in the hades.⁸⁸ Here by he proves that it is Jesus who gives eternal life.

3.2.6. Bread of Life

It is evident in the Gospel of John that the Bread of Life directly indicates Eucharist. Though Ephrem used this Eucharistic imagery separately in his works, he made a brilliant blend of the imageries of the Bread of Life and Medicine of Life. Here the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* is incorporated in the imagery of the Bread of Life. To explain the same, he takes various incidents from the Old Testament and the New Testament. He makes a symbolic blending to incorporate the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* with the imagery of the Bread of Life. And he instructs the faithful how to receive the Eucharist. He says that all those who have eaten from the unleavened bread provided in Egypt died, whereas the life-giving bread, *the Medicine of Life*, brings Life to everyone who receives it faithfully. And thereby, those people will be rewarded with eternal life.⁸⁹ Ephrem also warns the people to receive the Bread of Life with the proper disposition of the heart. Otherwise, it will cause eternal separation as if in the case of Judas.⁹⁰ Here he points out two facts;

- a. The unleavened bread received with the proper disposition of the heart in the Holy Qurbano is *the Medicine of Life*.
- b. When One receives the Eucharist with mortal sin, it becomes a deadly poison to that person.⁹¹

Ephrem wants to say that the Eucharist nourishes the body as well as the soul.

⁸⁸ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Nissibian Geethangal*, (Kottaym: OIRSI, 2009) 110.

⁸⁹ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 36.

⁹⁰ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 38.

⁹¹ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 40.

3.2.7. Influence from the Nature

Ephrem uses much imagery from nature. He also quotes all those imageries from the Bible itself. For example, Unleavened Bread ⁹², Fountain ⁹³, Medicine ⁹⁴, Fragrance ⁹⁵, Goat ⁹⁶, Fruit ⁹⁷, etc. Here St Ephrem has brilliantly used these images from nature and provided a shift in the meaning.

3.3. The influence of the Gospel of St John in the works of St Ephrem

The significance of this is very vital in understanding the concept of ‘life’ in the imagery of ‘*The Medicine of Life.*’ St John has made use of the idea of Life theologically to present the concept of eternal life, that is, Jesus Christ himself. According to him, Jesus is the resurrection and the Life. “Those who believe in me, even though they die, will live, and everyone who lives and believes in me will never die.”(Jn.11:25) It is clear from the quotes that the purpose of the incarnation of Jesus and his death on the Cross is to give Life.”(Jn.10:11). Life is not a static reality, whereas it is always active in its very nature because the creator of Life is dynamic and active. Life is a ‘language’ through which God speaks. The evangelist’s purpose in writing the Gospel is to give ‘Life’ to the world. (Jn.20:30) This theme is recurring in the works of St Ephrem. Therefore, the better analysis of the word ‘Life’ in the imagery of *the Medicine of Life becomes obvious with the interpretation of Psuche, Bios, and Zoe* in St John. All these Greek words are used for denoting ‘Life,’ but with different meanings. For example, *Zoe* means ‘divine life,’ whereas ‘Psyche’ means ‘natural life.’ Now let us evaluate how the fourth evangelist has made use of the word *Zoe* in

⁹² Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 20.

⁹³ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 26.

⁹⁴ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 36.

⁹⁵ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 33.

⁹⁶ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 68.

⁹⁷ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Kanyathva Geethangal*, 61.

his Gospel. According to the Beloved Disciple, in the book *The Gospel*,⁹⁸ we come across a few points that deal with the different shades of the word *Zoe*. Luke used the word *Bios* for “Life.” (Lk.8:14) The term *Bios* refers to the physical body, whereas Matthew has made use of the word *Psuche*. (Mt.16.25) Here Matthew has gone a little ahead of Luke, and we can see a transition of meaning from Physiological to the psychological Life of the humans. Here he refers to the Life of the soul. When we come to John, it is evident that he has gone to the depth to perfect the concept of “Life” by using the word “*Zoe*” (Jn.1:4). Here he explains how the divine Life was dispensed to the entire humanity through the incarnation and the paschal mysteries of Jesus Christ. He wants to prove that humans get participation in the divine Life in and through Jesus Christ. It is evident from here that the use of the word “Life” in the Gospel of John is different from that of the Synoptic Gospels. The following points will explain how John has changed the meaning of Life by using the words *Zoe*.

- a. **A life with which God lives:** “In Him was life [*zoe*], and the life [*zoe*] was the light of men.”(Jn.1:4) John wants to prove that eternal Life resides in the Triune God. We, the humans, become eligible for the divine Life only if God wills for the same. Therefore, whoever believes in him may have eternal **life**. (Jn. 3:15)
- b. **A life that Father and Son share:** John again says that eternal Life is shared among the persons in the Trinity. He indirectly proves “*Perichoresis*.” Therefore, God, the Father, willed to send His Son to have eternal Life for humanity who believes in Jesus Christ. “For God so loved the world, that he gave his only Son, that whoever believes in him should not perish but have eternal **life** [*zoen*].” (Jn.3:16)
- c. **The Son Himself is the Life:** After proving that God and Jesus Christ share the same Life, John teaches the people that “whoever believes in the

⁹⁸Cf. Maniparambil, Jose. *The Gospel According to the Beloved Disciple* (Bangalore: Claretian Publications, 2011) 201.

Son has eternal **life** [*zoen*] and whoever does not obey the Son shall not see **life** [*zoen*], but the wrath of God remains on him.” (Jn 3:36) Then John gives the account of the Samaritan Woman. There Jesus reveals himself to the Samaritan Woman that He is the source and summit of eternal Life. (Jn. 4:14) This account also indicates that salvation is not merely for the Israelites but all the nations.

- d. The same Life gained through Faith:** Then John says that the one who believes in Jesus Christ gains the Life through steady Faith. (Jn.5:24) That is, Peter promises Jesus that he is ready to give his Life for eternal Life. (Jn.6:68) It means that through Jesus, only one can enter into eternal Life. (Jn.14:6) Here the encounter with Jesus inspired or, better to say, transformed Peter to lay down his will or soul (*psuche*) to Jesus. (Jn.15:13) Here, Jesus teaches that the real friend of Jesus will submit the physical Life and the will (soul).
- e. The Spirit is the life principle:** John explains that the Holy Spirit is the life principle. Therefore, the sin against Holy Spirit may cease one from eternal Life. “It is the Spirit who gives life; the flesh is no help at all. The words that I have spoken to you are spirit and life.”(Jn.6:63)
- f. This gift of Spirit is associated with Baptism and is nourished by the Eucharist:** The eternal Life is imparted to the believer as the gift of the Holy Spirit at the time of Baptism, and the imparted Life is nourished with the Holy Eucharist. (Jn.6:35) “I am the living bread that came down from heaven. If anyone eats of this bread, he will live forever. And the bread that I will give for the life [*zōēs*] of the world is my flesh.” (Jn. 6:51) It means that the true Life is imparted to the believer is through Jesus Christ. And the imparting of the divine Life is continued in the Church through the Holy Eucharist. Therefore, John advises the faithful to approach the Body and Blood of Jesus with reverence and devotion.
- g. Life surpasses death:** The eternal Life imparted to humans with the power of the Holy Spirit will transcend death. “So Jesus said to them,

‘Truly, truly, I say to you, unless you eat the flesh of the Son of Man and drink his blood, you have no life [zoen] in you.’ Whoever feeds on my flesh and drinks my blood has eternal Life [zoen], and I will raise him on the last day.” Jn.6:53-54

- h. This Life can be taken away from the believer when he becomes an unbeliever:** The one who believes in Jesus Christ has eternal Life. Suppose anyone moves away from Jesus deliberately after realizing that He is the Life. In that case, that person will not participate in the LIFE because Jesus is the resurrection and the Life. (Jn.5:29)

The use of the Greek word “Zoe” in the Gospel of John is to prove that only God can impart eternal Life to humans alone, and John wants to communicate that the one who believes in Jesus Christ takes part in the divine Life. Therefore, John says that there should take place a kenotic transition to attain eternal Life. It means that one has to make a deliberate leap from “Bios” to “Zoe.” It happens only when one surrenders one’s physical and psychological lives before Jesus by admitting willfully that He is the LIFE. St Ephrem was using the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* in the same line with that of St John.

3.3. Conclusion

The tri-cultural influence leads St Ephrem to use the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* to bring out the theology of Eucharist. Since he was moving around biblical imageries, it was easy for the people to comprehend the theology of his writings, particularly that of the Eucharist. He conveys the message that all the revelations of God were fulfilled in Jesus Christ, and the abiding presence of Jesus Christ is continued through the Eucharist, *the Medicine of Life*.

The imagery *The Medicine of Life* is not simple imagery that deals with the physical Life, whereas it goes far beyond its meaning through the poetical works of St Ephrem. The imagery of *The Medicine of Life* has been interpreted with existing meaning to elucidate the Eucharist's mystery. He wants to convey that

the Eucharist is the actual Medicine of Life, Jesus Christ. The application of the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* has another Eucharistic dimension. That is, the source and means of 'Life' are the same. It means that Christ is the source and Christ is the means. He vividly presents that Jesus is the healer and the medicine by which one is granted 'life.' Therefore, the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* is personified with the Person Jesus Christ.

St Ephrem makes a lot of comparisons with the Old testament incidents and imageries to convey the message that the people must have widened their thinking horizon (neuro-context) in the light of Faith to incorporate the mysteries of salvation. He uses all these comparisons to substantiate the fact that participating in the Holy Eucharist is the prefiguration of the *Parousia*. To convey this message, he says, "Whoever has eaten the life-giving bread of the Son will be taken to the heavens to welcome Him. (own translation)"⁹⁹ St Ephrem brings the eschatological dimension of the Eucharist by using the imagery of *the Medicine of Life*. He says that when Jesus consecrated the bread and the wine, it became *the Medicine of Life* to those who receive them with Faith.¹⁰⁰

The fall of the first parents caused the forfeiture of the robe of glory. Humanity lost the divine Life with this fall, and no one could gain it with merit. Therefore, God sends Jesus Christ to this world to grant the participation in the divine Life of humanity through Him. And whenever we take part in the Holy Eucharist with the proper disposition of the heart, we take part in the divine Life by being in this world that continues after death. If the Eucharist is Christ, then we are partaking in the divine Life through Him, and therefore He is *the Medicine of Life*. When we live in the grace of God, even after our death, we continue the same. Thus, the Eucharistic interpretation of the particular

⁹⁹ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 36.

¹⁰⁰ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 28.

Judgement reveals that we can partake in the divine Life through Jesus Christ. Again, in the universal judgment, we receive the enlightenment that all those who witnessed Jesus Christ directly or indirectly are saved through Him. If the loss of divine Life is death, then gaining Life is nothing but being in Christ. Thus, St Ephrem wants to convey the same message through the Eucharistic imagery of *the Medicine of Life*.

This chapter mainly focused on the different traits of the Eucharistic imagery, *the Medicine of Life* such as mercy, purification, source of Life, and so on, along with how these characteristics are associated with Eucharist to bring out the Eucharistic theology of St Ephrem. In other words, this chapter explained how the shift of meaning occurs through imageries and symbols. It means that imageries and symbols bring a kind of semantic shift (Transcendental Leap) to religious and theological language. This semantic shift is conveyed and appropriately understood only within the neuro-context of the text. It means that without getting into the neuro-context of the text, it becomes difficult to extract the intended meaning. Here it is very evident from the works of St Ephrem that the Johannine theology of 'Life' has influenced the theological thinking and writings of St Ephrem a lot. When the poetical works of St Ephrem are analyzed within the Johannine spectrum, it becomes evident that the meaning of the said Eucharistic imagery becomes an indicator of the mystery of the economy of salvation too. All the semantic shifts of the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* are analyzed in the General Conclusion.

GENERAL CONCLUSION

This chapter mainly focuses on the semantic shift of the Eucharistic imagery *the Medicine of Life*. Here, the crux of the discussion is about how the change in meaning occurs through the use of imageries and symbols. As I stated in the general introduction, imageries and symbols bring a kind of semantic shift (Transcendental Leap) to religious and theological language. This semantic shift is conveyed and appropriately understood only within the neuro-context of the text. It means that without getting into the neuro-context of the text, it becomes difficult to extract the intended meaning. As stated in the previous chapter, the works of St Ephrem have been highly influenced by the Johannine theology, especially that of 'Life.' Now, we are going to analyze all semantic shifts of the imagery of *the Medicine of Life*.

Medicine is part and parcel of human Life. It is through medicine by which a person is cured of the ailment and even from death. Mythological explanations on medicine bring the idea of immortality (*Amrith*- an elixir of Life) and medicine that brings one from death (*mruthasanjeevani*). As stated previously, St Ephrem uses the imagery of *the Medicine of Life* to qualify the Holy Eucharist with a different perspective. But my concern is concerning the processes of this paradigmatic grafting.¹⁰¹ Before getting into the topic, it is necessary to introduce a few terms such as 'neuro-context', 'Transcendental Leap,' etc. Neuro-context is the totality of our thinking.

Since the process of thinking is a continuous activity of the brain, the limits of the neuro- context cannot be limited. Neuro-context is permanently active. For example, when Shakespeare writes a poem and publishes it, it becomes a small part of his neuro-context (fragmentary neuro- context). As I stated above, this

¹⁰¹ "Paradigmatic grafting is a process where cognitive science builds new explanations by cobbling together old ones from multiple discipline." Cf. Aaron C.T., *Thinking about Religion: Extending the Cognitive Science of Religion*, 76.

fragmentary neuro- context has the potency of expanding its meaning following the context. Here the context can be another neuro- context or a group of neuro- contexts (collective neuro- context). When I, as a seminarian, read the said poem without knowing the exact background, I will interpret the same within my neuro- context. In cognitive science, it is called paradigmatic grafting. It means that any neuro- context out of the human brain can be considered as fragmentary neuro- context. It means that we are living in the matrix of neuro- context. All revelations occur within the matrix of a neuro- context. Sometimes, the same happens within the individual neuro- context or the collective neuro- context. Incorporating two different neuro- contexts leads to the phenomena of transcendental Leap (Transcendental Leap denotes the shift of meaning of a word from one to another). Specifically, it's a phenomenon of associating metaphysical meaning to the concrete reality or extracting esoteric meaning from concrete reality at the morpheme level (in the case of language, 'Morpheme is the smallest meaningful unit of a word.') and sensory level. Whatever we experience through our senses is coded with cultural code, and that is language. Every impression in the brain is transmitted to the other person through language. The language here means that which mediates in transferring a message from one person to another. It means that language cannot be confined within the limits of written or spoken words alone. It also includes illustrations, gesticulations, and expressions, and so on. Here I give prominence to the verbal language and try to analyze how the phenomenon of transcendental leap takes place.

The human brain is a storehouse. It has the internal mechanism to create new ideas with the available memories through association and dissociation. This is called "Neuro- context." One person understands a new thing within the existing Neuro- context. It means that Neuro- context is dynamic, and therefore all the data stored in the brain will be updated regularly. Thus, the phenomenon of the transcendental leap of a word takes place within the existing Neuro- context of

the person who is exposed to that particular word. If a person hears a new word, he understands its meaning with the help of the Neuro-context. It means that the internal mechanism of the existing Neuro-context will improve the existing idea. It is the time when the transcendental leap occurs. At this time, the meaning of a concrete reality will shift with the Transcendental Leap phenomenon. For example, the meaning of the word “Throne” is understood at different levels.

- a. **Child:** A place to sit
- b. **Teenager:** A place where a king sits
- c. **Adult:** A symbol of power
- d. **Theologian:** Symbol of God’s majesty, rule, Kingdom, presence, authority, etc.

Here in this example, when the word “Throne” is introduced to a child, the child interprets the word with the existing Neuro-context and expands the Neuro-context. In the later stages, the aspect of Kingdom, King Etc. are taught to the child, and when the child becomes a teenager, the same word gets its meaning widened. This is the same case when that child becomes a theologian. The change of meaning is very evident in the given an example. It means that a person is programmed within a culture. A person is formed within a culture to which they are exposed. When that person hears, reads, sees, touches, and smells something, that will be interpreted within the Neuro-context. Therefore, a better understanding of that person necessitates the proper understanding of the culture where he or she was born and brought up and the cultures to which that person is exposed. With this introductory note, I try to analyze the transcendental leap of the imagery, “*the Medicine of Life*,” to find out its transcendental leap to the Eucharistic Imagery.

Transcendental Leap of “*the Medicine of Life*”: The transcendental leap of the Eucharistic imagery- *the Medicine of Life* results from the expansion of the

Neuro –context. Preliminarily St Ephrem was born and brought up in a place where Christianity was rooted well. From his writings, it is very evident that he was well versed with the Old Testament and New Testament. He lived in a situation where Arianism was propagated by the heretic teachers (Arianism¹⁰²). The poetical works of St Ephrem are an attempt to teach the true Faith. Therefore, the imagery of *Medicine Life* symbolizes Eucharist. St Ephrem tried to bring forth all the teachings and doctrines on Faith to the Eucharistic imagery, *the Medicine of Life*.

Ephrem considers even the incarnation of Jesus Christ is *the Medicine of Life* in his *Hymns on Nativity*. He expresses the soteriological aspect of the imagery, *the Medicine of Life*, by stating that those who consumed the ever-living Bread of the Son will be raised to the heavens to welcome him.¹⁰³ These expressions show that St Ephrem was well aware of the doctrines of Faith, and therefore he used imagery familiar to the people to explain the Eucharistic mysteries. When we analyze the imagery of *Medicine of Life*, it is evident that the neuro- context of St Ephrem was defined with that of the scripture writers; especially with that of the fourth evangelist St. John. According to St John, the transcendental leap of the imagery the Medicine of Life became possible through the deep meditation of the Gospel.

Now I will explain how the Eucharistic imagery of *the Medicine of Life* gets an eschatological transcendental leap. If Church is the mystical Body of Christ, the congregation that takes part in the Eucharist is also part of the mystical Body of Christ. If the Holy Eucharist is the Christ, when we receive that Holy Eucharist

¹⁰² Arianism was propagated by Arius (250-). It is a doctrine that denied the divinity of the LOGOS. It originated in Alexandria. Arius taught that Jesus is the supreme of all the creatures of God and he refused that LOGOS was from the same substance as God the Father. Therefore, there was a time when Son was not.

¹⁰³ Cf. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 36.

with the proper disposition of the heart, we are partaking in the divine Life which is already but not yet.

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